

Electronic Companion to: Decentralized Failure-Tolerant Optimization of Electric Vehicle Charging

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EC.1. EV CHARGING STATION CONSTRAINTS

This section presents the constraints defining the feasible operation domain of charging stations $\mathcal{D}_s, s \in \mathcal{S}$. Let $\mathcal{V}(s)$ be the set of EVs connected to station s at any interval in the horizon \mathcal{T} ; $p_{v,t}, r_{v,t}^{\text{spin}}$ be, respectively, the power draw and spinning reserve provision of EV v at interval t ; $r_{s,t}^{\text{recov}}$ be the power recovery for energy provided in activated spinning reserves of EV v at interval t (recovering energy of reserves activated at $\tau < t$); \mathcal{D}_v be the feasible charge/discharge domain of EV $v \in \mathcal{V}$; and Λ be the probability of spinning reserve activation (identical for all stations and intervals). Then, we define domain \mathcal{D}_s as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_s = & \left\{ (\mathbf{p}^{\max}, \mathbf{p}^{\mathbb{E}}, \mathbf{r}^{\text{spin}}) \in \mathbb{R}^T \times \mathbb{R}^T \times \mathbb{R}^T \mid \right. \\ & \exists (\mathbf{p}_v, \mathbf{r}_v^{\text{spin}}, \mathbf{r}_v^{\text{recov}}) \in \mathcal{D}_v \forall v \in \mathcal{V}(s) : \\ & p_t^{\max} = \sum_{\substack{v \in \mathcal{V}(s): \\ \mathcal{T}(v) \ni t}} (p_{v,t} + r_{v,t}^{\text{recov}}), \\ & p_t^{\mathbb{E}} = \sum_{\substack{v \in \mathcal{V}(s): \\ \mathcal{T}(v) \ni t}} (p_{v,t} - \Lambda \cdot r_{v,t}^{\text{spin}} + \Lambda \cdot r_{v,t}^{\text{recov}}), \\ & r_t^{\text{spin}} = \sum_{\substack{v \in \mathcal{V}(s): \\ \mathcal{T}(v) \ni t}} r_{v,t}^{\text{spin}}, p_t^{\max} \leq P_s^{\max}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \left. \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{ec.1})$$

The first constraint in (ec.1) defines the maximum draw of station s as the sum of the draws and reserve recovery of all its connected EVs, which is indeed the worst case for each interval $t \in \mathcal{T}$: EVs draw their planned power and an additional amount to compensate for spinning reserves provided in previous intervals, without the reduction that would be caused by the activation of reserves in the current interval. The second constraint aggregates the expected draw of every EV at the station, considering the reserve activation probability Λ into the station expected draw, and the third constraint aggregates spinning reserve provisions in the same fashion. The fourth constraint makes sure that the station's maximum power draw does not exceed the station's capacity.

We define the charge/discharge domain \mathcal{D}_v of each EV $v \in \mathcal{V}$ as follows. Let $P_v^{\max}, E_v^{\max}, \eta_v$ be, respectively, the maximum power draw, energy storage capacity, and charging efficiency of v ; $T_v^{\text{plug}}, T_v^{\text{unplug}}$ be the plug/unplug intervals of v and $\mathcal{T}(v) = \{T_v^{\text{plug}}, \dots, T_v^{\text{unplug}}\}$ be the set of intervals v is

connected to its station; $E_v^{\text{plug}}, E_v^{\text{unplug}}$ be the SOC at T_v^{plug} and the target SOC at T_v^{unplug} ; $q_{t,\tau}^{\text{recov}}$ be the recovery at interval t for reserve provided at interval $\tau < t$; and TR is the maximum allowed lag between reserve activation and recovery (e.g. if spinning reserve is activated at interval τ , all energy spent in the activation must be recovered by $\tau + TR$). Domain \mathcal{D}_v is, then, defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_v = & \left\{ (\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r}^{\text{spin}}, \mathbf{r}^{\text{recov}}) \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{T}(v)|} \times \mathbb{R}_+^{|\mathcal{T}(v)|} \times \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{T}(v)|} \mid \right. \\ & \exists \mathbf{q}_t^{\text{recov}} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{\min\{T_v^{\text{unplug}} - t, TR\}} \forall t \in \mathcal{T}(v) \setminus T_v^{\text{unplug}} : \\ & 0 \leq p_t - r_t^{\text{spin}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}(v), \\ & p_t + \sum_{\tau=\max\{T_v^{\text{plug}}, t-TR\}}^{t-1} q_{\tau,t}^{\text{recov}} \leq P_v^{\max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}(v), \\ & r_t^{\text{spin}} = \sum_{\tau=t+1}^{\min\{T_v^{\text{unplug}}, t+TR\}} q_{t,\tau}^{\text{recov}} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}(v), \\ & E_v^{\text{unplug}} \leq E_v^{\text{plug}} + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}(v)} \eta_v \cdot p_t \leq E_v^{\max} \left. \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{ec.2})$$

The first constraint in (ec.2) ensures that the power draw is always positive, even if spinning reserve is activated (we are only capturing existing VIG technology), while the second constraint ensures that the maximum power draw is not exceeded, even when recovering energy from previously activated reserves. The third constraint guarantees that if reserve is activated at a certain interval, the energy lost to reserves can be recovered in the coming TR intervals. The fourth constraint ensures that the target SOC is met and that the storage capacity is respected.

EC.2. PROOFS

Proof of Prop. 1. We will show that the pair $(\mathbf{u}_{\mathcal{S}(f),t}^{k+1}, \alpha_{f,t}^\dagger)$, as defined in Prop. 1, is a primal-dual solution to the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker¹ (KKT) conditions of problem (10), which can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \alpha_{f,t} & \perp \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}(f)} u_{s,t} \leq P_{f,t}, \\ u_{s,t} & = p_{s,t}^{\max,k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} \mu_{s,t}^k - \frac{1}{\rho} \alpha_{f,t} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}(f), \end{aligned}$$

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¹Recall that Karush-Kuhn-Tucker conditions are necessary and sufficient conditions for optimality of convex programs with linear constraints.

and, using the definitions of Prop. 1, reduce to:

$$0 \leq \alpha_{f,t} \perp \frac{|\mathcal{S}(f)|}{\rho} \alpha_{f,t} \geq \chi_{f,t} - P_{f,t}.$$

There are two possible cases depending on the values of $\chi_{f,t}$:

- $\chi_{f,t} \leq P_{f,t}$. Then, $\alpha_{f,t} = 0$, $u_{s,t} = \tilde{u}_{s,t}$, for all $s \in \mathcal{S}(f)$, satisfies the KKT system.
- $\chi_{f,t} > P_{f,t}$. Then $\alpha_{f,t} = (\rho/|\mathcal{S}(f)|)(\chi_{f,t} - P_{f,t})$, $u_{s,t} = \tilde{u}_{s,t} - (1/N)(\chi_{f,t} - P_{f,t})$, for all $s \in \mathcal{S}(f)$, satisfies the KKT system.

Hence, $\alpha_{f,t} = \alpha_{f,t}^\dagger = (\rho/|\mathcal{S}(f)|)(\chi_{f,t} - P_{f,t})_+$, $u_{s,t} = u_{s,t}^{k+1} = \tilde{u}_{s,t} - (1/\rho)\alpha_{f,t}^\dagger$, for all $s \in \mathcal{S}(f)$, always satisfies the KKT system of problem (10). \square

Proof of Prop. 2. We will show that problems (11) and (15) are equivalent. More precisely, we show that the space of optimal solutions on (θ_m, β_m) of both problems coincide, and further, that $v_{\mathcal{S}(m)}$ is implied by β_m . The equivalence proof is based upon the KKT conditions of both problems, which we present in the following. The KKT conditions of problem (11) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \beta_m \perp \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}(m)} v_s \leq \theta_m, \mathbf{1}_{T \times 1}, \\ v_s &= p_s^{\mathbb{E}, k+1} + \frac{1}{\rho} v_s^k - \frac{1}{\rho} \beta_m \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}(m), \\ \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \beta_{m,t} &= \Pi_m^{\text{peak}}. \end{aligned}$$

It is clear, from the second condition, that the value of $v_{\mathcal{S}(m)}$ is implied by β_m . Substituting v_s from the second condition onto the first, we obtain the following reduced optimality conditions for problem (11):

$$0 \leq \beta_m \perp \psi_m - \frac{|\mathcal{S}(m)|}{\rho} \beta_m \leq \theta_m \mathbf{1}_{T \times 1}, \quad \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \beta_{m,t} = \Pi_m^{\text{peak}}. \quad (\text{ec.3})$$

The KKT conditions of problem (15), on the other hand, can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \beta_m \perp \eta \mathbf{1}_{T \times 1} \geq \frac{|\mathcal{S}(m)|}{\rho} \zeta, \\ 0 &\leq \zeta \perp \psi_m - \frac{|\mathcal{S}(m)|}{\rho} \beta_m \leq \theta_m \mathbf{1}_{T \times 1}, \quad (\text{ec.4}) \\ \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \zeta_t &= 1, \quad \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \beta_{m,t} = \Pi_m^{\text{peak}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}^T$ and $\eta \in \mathbb{R}$ are dual variables of the linear constraints of (15).

Let $A = \{(\theta_m, \beta_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{1+T} \mid (\text{ec.3})\}$ and $B = \{(\theta_m, \beta_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{1+T} \mid \exists (\eta, \zeta) \in \mathbb{R}^{1+T} : (\text{ec.4})\}$. We can show the following:

- $A \subseteq B$. To see this, let $(\bar{\theta}_m, \bar{\beta}_m) \in A$, $\mathcal{T}^0 = \{t \mid \bar{\beta}_{m,t} = 0\}$, and $\mathcal{T}^1 = \{t \mid \bar{\beta}_{m,t} > 0\}$. Note that $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m) \in A \implies |\mathcal{T}^1| \geq 1$. Then, we can construct $\bar{\eta}$ and $\bar{\zeta}$ such that $(\bar{\theta}_m, \bar{\beta}_m, \bar{\eta}, \bar{\zeta})$ solves (ec.4) as: $\bar{\eta} = |\mathcal{S}(m)|/(\rho|\mathcal{T}^1|)$, $\bar{\zeta}_t = 0 \forall t \in \mathcal{T}^0$, $\bar{\zeta}_t = 1/|\mathcal{T}^1| \forall t \in \mathcal{T}^1$. Thus, $(\bar{\theta}_m, \bar{\beta}_m) \in B$.
- $B \subseteq A$. Let $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m) \in B$. It is clear that $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m)$ satisfies all linear equalities and inequalities in (ec.3),

as those are also present in (ec.4). It remains to show that $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m)$ satisfies the complementarity condition $\beta_m \perp \psi_m - (|\mathcal{S}(m)|/\rho)\beta_m - \theta_m \mathbf{1}_{T \times 1}$. We will proceed by contradiction. Assume $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m)$ does not satisfy the aforementioned complementarity condition, thus there exists a $t \in \mathcal{T}$ for which $\bar{\beta}_{m,t} > 0$ and $\psi_{m,t} - (|\mathcal{S}(m)|/\rho)\bar{\beta}_{m,t} < \bar{\theta}_m$. However, $\eta \geq 1/\rho$, therefore, $\bar{\beta}_{m,t} > 0 \implies \eta = (|\mathcal{S}(m)|/\rho)\zeta_{m,t} \implies \zeta_{m,t} \geq 1/|\mathcal{S}(m)| \implies \psi_{m,t} - (|\mathcal{S}(m)|/\rho)\bar{\beta}_{m,t} = \bar{\theta}_m$, a contradiction. Thus, $(\bar{z}_m, \bar{\beta}_m) \in A$.

Therefore, $A = B$, which concludes our proof. \square

Proof of Prop. 3. The proof proceeds by presenting a greedy heuristic for problem (15) and, then, showing that it always produces an optimal solution. Let $z = \rho/(|\mathcal{S}(m)| \cdot \Pi_m^{\text{peak}}) \theta_m$, $D = \rho/(|\mathcal{S}(m)| \cdot \Pi_m^{\text{peak}}) \psi_m$, and $x = 1/\Pi_m^{\text{peak}} \beta_m$, then problem (15) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{z,x} \quad & z \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & z \geq D_t - x_t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \\ & \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} x_t = 1, \quad x \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{ec.5})$$

for which any optimal solution must satisfy

$$0 \leq x_t \perp z + x_t \geq D_t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \quad \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} x_t = 1, \quad (\text{ec.6})$$

due to Prop. 2. We construct a candidate solution (z^H, x^H) to (ec.5) through the following greedy heuristic:

- 1) Compute a decreasing order permutation $i(\cdot)$ for D ($D_{i(s)} \geq D_{i(t)}$ iff $i(s) \leq i(t)$, for $s, t \in \mathcal{T}$).
- 2) Let $k = 2$, $r = 1$ and $z^H = D_{i(1)}$.
- 3) If $k \leq T$ and $(k-1)(D_{i(k)} - D_{i(k-1)}) \leq r$ then:
 - Let $z^H = D_{i(k)}$, $r = r - (k-1)(D_{i(k-1)} - D_{i(k)})$.
 - else:
 - Let $z^H = z^H - r/(k-1)$, $r = 0$.
- 4) If $r > 0$ then: let $k = k + 1$ and return to 3.
- 5) Let $x_t^H = \max\{0, D_t - z^H\} \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$.

We claim that (z^H, x^H) satisfies (ec.6) and, therefore, it is optimal for (ec.5). To see this, observe that inequality and complementarity constraints of (ec.6) are trivially satisfied by (z^H, x^H) . It remains to show that $\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} x_t^H = 1$. Let k^H be the last k on which the condition of step 3 holds, then

$$z^H = D_{i(k^H)} - \frac{1}{k^H} \left(1 - \sum_{k=2}^{k^H} (k-1)(D_{i(k)} - D_{i(k-1)}) \right),$$

thus

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} x_t &= \sum_{k=1}^{k^H} D_{i(k)} - k^H z^H \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{k^H} (D_{i(k)} - D_{i(k^H)}) - \\ &\quad \sum_{k=2}^{k^H} (k-1)(D_{i(k-1)} - D_{i(k)}) + 1 = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, (z^H, \mathbf{x}^H) is optimal for (ec.5). Optimal solutions for (15) can be found by simply scaling (z^H, \mathbf{x}^H) as indicated in the beginning of this proof.

Finally, counting the worst-case number of operations of our optimal heuristic we have: $T \log T$ comparisons for sorting in step 1; $2T$ assignments in steps 3 and 4; and T assignments in step 5. Dropping linear terms, problem (15) worst-case time complexity is, at most, $\mathcal{O}(T \log T)$. \square

Proof of Prop. 4. Omitted for brevity. Mild extension to proof of Prop. 1. \square

Proof of Lemma 1. We will show that the sequence of iterates of the decentralized ADMM algorithm (Fig. 3) is identical to that of the distributed ADMM algorithm (Fig. 2), which is known to converge to the optimal solution [1]. First, observe that by the *first prox theorem* [2], the optimal solution to subproblems (9)–(12) is unique in the space of variables they update, that is: $\mathbf{p}_s^{\max, k+1}, \mathbf{p}_s^{\mathbb{E}, k+1}, \mathbf{r}_{s, \mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}}}^{\text{spin}, k+1}$ is the unique optimal of subproblem (9), $\mathbf{u}_{\mathcal{S}(f), t}^{k+1}$ is the unique optimal of subproblem (10), $\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{S}(m)}^{k+1}$ is the unique optimal of subproblem (11), and $\mathbf{w}_{\mathcal{S}(g), t}^{k+1}$ is the unique optimal of subproblem (12). This, on the one hand, implies that the sequence of iterates of the distributed ADMM algorithm is unique for a given starting point and $\rho > 0$. At the same time, because Propositions 1, 2, and 4 guarantee that the solutions to subproblems (10)–(12) obtained via local computations and reduction operations in the decentralized ADMM algorithm (steps 4–13 of Fig. 3) are optimal, they must be the same as those found by solving subproblems (10)–(12) in the distributed ADMM algorithm. Therefore, the decentralized ADMM algorithm computes the same updates and follows the same sequence of iterates as the distributed ADMM algorithm, when initialized at the same starting point and with the same parameter $\rho > 0$. \square

Proof of Lemma 2. Let k^{fail} be the first (finite) iteration count at which all stations $s \in \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}$ have failed. Additionally, consider the optimal EV charging problem without the stations in $\mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}$:

$$\min_{\substack{p, r \\ u, v, w \\ \theta, \phi}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}} \left(\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \Pi_{m(s), t}^{\text{energy}} p_{s, t}^{\mathbb{E}} - \sum_{t = \mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}} + 1}^T \Pi_{g(s), t}^{\text{spin}} r_{s, t}^{\text{spin}} \right) + \sum_{\substack{m \in \mathcal{M}: \\ \mathcal{S}(m) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \neq \emptyset}} \Pi_m^{\text{peak}} \theta_m + \sum_{\substack{g \in \mathcal{G}: \\ \mathcal{S}(g) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \neq \emptyset}} \sum_{t=1}^{\mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}}} \Pi_g^{\text{fail}} \phi_{g, t} \quad (\text{ec.7})$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}(f) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}} u_{s, t} \leq P_{f, t} \quad \forall f \in \mathcal{F} : \mathcal{S}(f) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \neq \emptyset, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (\text{ec.8})$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}(m) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}} v_{s, t} \leq \theta_m \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} : \mathcal{S}(m) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \neq \emptyset, t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (\text{ec.9})$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}(g) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}} w_{s, t} \geq R_{g, t}^{\text{spin}} - \phi_{g, t} \quad \forall g \in \mathcal{G} : \mathcal{S}(g) \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \neq \emptyset, t \in \mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}} \quad (\text{ec.10})$$

$$\mathbf{p}_s^{\max} = \mathbf{u}_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \quad (\boldsymbol{\mu}_s) \quad (\text{ec.11})$$

$$\mathbf{p}_s^{\mathbb{E}} = \mathbf{v}_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \quad (\boldsymbol{\nu}_s) \quad (\text{ec.12})$$

$$\mathbf{r}_{s, \mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}}}^{\text{spin}} = \mathbf{w}_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}} \quad (\boldsymbol{\xi}_s) \quad (\text{ec.13})$$

$$(\mathbf{p}_s^{\max}, \mathbf{p}_s^{\mathbb{E}}, \mathbf{r}_{s, \mathcal{T}^{\text{spin}}}^{\text{spin}}) \in \mathcal{D}_s \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^{\text{fail}}. \quad (\text{ec.14})$$

Denote *failing sequence* to the sequence of iterates of the decentralized ADMM algorithm applied to problem (1) – (8) with failures, and *modified sequence* to the sequence of iterates of the decentralized algorithm applied to the modified problem (ec.7) – (ec.14) initialized from the k^{fail} -th iterate of the *failing sequence* and using the same $\rho > 0$ as the one used to generate the *failing sequence*. First, observe that the *failing sequence* continues beyond $k = k^{\text{fail}}$ because the communications graph remains strongly connected, allowing for reduction operations to be performed (i.e. the process does not terminate, nor it has an unspecified behavior after the failures have occurred). Furthermore, note that the $(k^{\text{fail}} + 1)$ -th element of the *failing sequence* is identical to the first element of the *modified sequence*, as the steps carried out by the decentralized ADMM algorithm after failures for the original problem at iteration $k = k^{\text{fail}} + 1$ are the same as those to be carried out by the decentralized ADMM algorithm over the modified problem (ec.7) – (ec.14) at iteration $k = 1$. The same applies to all later iterates, i.e. for any $i \in \mathbb{N}, i > 0$ we have that the $k^{\text{fail}} + i$ -th iterate of the *failing sequence* is identical to i -th iterate of the *modified sequence*.

By Lemma 1 the *modified sequence* converges to an optimal solution of (ec.7) – (ec.14). Therefore, the *failing sequence* also must converge to an optimal solution of problem (ec.7) – (ec.14), which concludes our proof. \square

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